

Date	Folder / Type of document	Title of document (Portuguese / English)	Description of document content	Access link
6/7/2010	Information on formulation process	Process # 00106.014812-2023-59	Brazil's voluntary submission to the OECD assessment of the integrity system of the federal public administration in 2010.	https://buscalai.cgu.gov.br/PedidosLai/DetailPePedido?id=5829108
9/27/2010	Information on formulation process	Process # 00106.014804-2023-11	CGU processes and documents that led to the OECD Integrity Review of Brazil: <i>Managing Risks for a Cleaner Public Service</i> (2011).	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19582555
10/27/2011	Publication on free press or government websites	OCDE elogia esforços do Brasil para melhorar integridade da administração pública	The OECD praised Brazil's efforts to strengthen integrity in public administration, highlighting the CGU's role and legal advances such as the Access to Information Law.	https://www.gov.br/cgu/pt-br/assuntos/noticias/2011/10/ocde-elogia-esforcos-do-brasil-para-melhorar-integridade-da-administracao-publica
11/12/2012	International standards / assessments	OECD Integrity Review of Brazil: Managing for a Cleaner Public Service	This review assesses Brazil's public integrity system and provides targeted recommendations to strengthen the ethics infrastructure, internal controls, and corruption prevention mechanisms across the federal administration.	https://www.oecd.org/content/dam/oecd/en/publications/reports/2012/11/oecd-integrity-review-of-brazil_g1q14801/9789264119321-en.pdf
8/2/2013	Brazilian norm	Lei nº 12.846	Provides for the strict administrative and civil liability of legal entities for acts against the domestic or foreign public administration, known as the Anti-Corruption Law.	http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/ato2011-2014/2013/lei/l12846.htm
5/1/2015	CGU guidance	Guia de Implantação de Programa de Integridade nas Estatais	Supports state-owned enterprises in designing and implementing integrity programs, especially within the scope of Law No. 12,846/2013, with a focus on corruption prevention and sound governance practices.	https://www.gov.br/cgu/pt-br/centrais-de-conteudo/publicacoes/integridade/arquivos/guia_estatais_final.pdf
3/18/2016	Information on formulation process	Process # 00106.018548-2023-22	CGU participants in the SPIO-OECD meetings.	https://buscalai.cgu.gov.br/PedidosLai/DetailPePedido?id=6110576
4/24/2016	Information on formulation process	Process # 00106.002086/2024-11	Formulation process of CGU Ordinance No. 784, of April 24, 2016.	https://buscalai.cgu.gov.br/PedidosLai/DetailPePedido?id=6874588
4/29/2016	Publication on free press or government websites	CGU lança programa de incentivo à integridade para ministérios	The CGU launched the Public Integrity Promotion Program (Profip) to help federal agencies implement anti-corruption compliance programs using risk-based approaches.	https://www.gov.br/cgu/pt-br/assuntos/noticias/2016/04/cgu-lanca-programa-de-incentivo-a-integridade-para-ministerios
4/29/2016	Brazilian norm	Portaria CGU nº 784	Establishes and regulates the Public Integrity Promotion Program (Profip) within the Federal Executive Branch. Revoked by Ordinance No. 1,827/2017.	https://repositorio.cgu.gov.br/bitstream/1/33996/12/2016_cgu_portaria_cgu_784_2016_fomento_integridade_publica.pdf
5/5/2016	Information on formulation process	Process # 00106.018546-2023-33	Formulation process of Joint Normative Instruction MP/CGU No. 01, of May 10, 2016.	https://buscalai.cgu.gov.br/PedidosLai/DetailPePedido?id=6110545
5/5/2016	Information on formulation process	Process # 18002.002667-2023-97	Formulation process of Joint Normative Instruction MP/CGU No. 01, of May 10, 2016.	https://buscalai.cgu.gov.br/PedidosLai/DetailPePedido?id=6110547
5/11/2016	Brazilian norm	Instrução Normativa Conjunta CGU/MP nº 1	Provides for internal controls, risk management, and governance within the Federal Executive Branch.	https://repositorio.cgu.gov.br/bitstream/1/33947/8/Instrucao%20Normativa%20Conjunta%20MP-CGU%2001-2016.pdf
7/1/2016	Brazilian norm	Lei nº 13.303	Provides the legal framework for state-owned enterprises, mixed-capital companies, and subsidiaries, including requirements for integrity and governance programs.	https://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/ato2015-2018/2016/lei/l13303.htm
11/1/2016	Publication on free press or government websites	Ministério da Transparência lança Programa de Integridade	On October 31, 2016, the CGU launched its own integrity program based on Profip.	https://www.gov.br/cgu/pt-br/assuntos/noticias/2016/11/ministerio-da-transparencia-lanca-programa-de-integridade

12/26/2016	Publication on free press or government websites	Ministério da Transparência realiza oficina para implantação de programas de integridade	A pilot workshop in Belo Horizonte trained civil servants from federal institutions to develop integrity programs, combining practical and theoretical components.	https://www.gov.br/cgu/pt-br/assuntos/noticias/2016/12/ministerio-da-transparencia-realiza-oficina-para-implantacao-de-programas-de-integridade
1/26/2017	International standards / assessments	Recommendation of the Council on Public Integrity	This OECD legal instrument provides a strategic framework for promoting public integrity, shifting from reactive policies to proactive, risk-based strategies focused on systems, culture, and accountability across all levels of government and society.	https://legalinstruments.oecd.org/en/instruments/OECD-LEGAL-0435
5/1/2017	CGU guidance	Como Fortalecer sua Gestão: Lei Anticorrupção e Programa de Integridade	Introduces municipal public managers to the fundamentals of Law No. 12,846/2013 and the benefits of implementing integrity programs as preventive tools and promoters of ethics.	https://www.gov.br/cgu/pt-br/centrais-de-conteudo/publicacoes/transparencia-publica/colecao-municipio-transparente/arquivos/como-fortalecer-sua-gestao-lei-anti-corrupcao-e-programa-de-integridade.pdf
5/1/2017	CGU guidance	Como Implementar uma Corregedoria em Municípios – Versão Intermediária	A summarized version aimed at municipalities with intermediate institutional capacity, covering structure, responsibilities, and recommended practices for establishing internal affairs offices.	https://www.gov.br/cgu/pt-br/centrais-de-conteudo/publicacoes/transparencia-publica/colecao-municipio-transparente/arquivos/como-implementar-uma-corregedoria-em-municipios_simplificada.pdf
7/1/2017	CGU guidance	Cartilha: Sugestões de Decretos para Regulamentação da Lei Anticorrupção nos Municípios	Offers model decrees and legal recommendations to help municipalities regulate the implementation of Law No. 12,846/2013, with the aim of ensuring legal certainty and local standardization.	https://www.gov.br/cgu/pt-br/centrais-de-conteudo/publicacoes/transparencia-publica/colecao-municipio-transparente/arquivos/cartilha-sugestoes-de-decretos-para-a-regulamentacao-da-lei-anticorrupcao-nos-municipios.pdf
7/1/2017	CGU guidance	Manual para Implementação de Programas de Integridade	A general and illustrative guide designed to help various organizations, including states and municipalities, implement integrity programs based on best practices and legal standards.	https://www.gov.br/cgu/pt-br/centrais-de-conteudo/publicacoes/integridade/arquivos/manual_profip.pdf
8/8/2017	Information on formulation process	Process # 00106.002365/2024-76	Formulation process of CGU Ordinance No. 1,827, of August 23, 2017.	https://buscalai.cgu.gov.br/PedidosLai/DetailePedido?id=6901186
9/4/2017	Brazilian norm	Portaria CGU nº 1.827	Establishes the new Public Integrity Promotion Program (Profip), replacing Ordinance No. 784/2016, with guidelines for developing integrity plans in federal executive agencies and entities.	https://repositorio.cgu.gov.br/bitstream/1/41672/18/portaria-1827-cgu.pdf
10/10/2017	Information on formulation process	Process # 00106.018541-2023-19	Formulation process of Decree No. 9,203, of November 22, 2017.	https://buscalai.cgu.gov.br/PedidosLai/DetailePedido?id=6110531
10/23/2017	Information on formulation process	Process # 18002.002664-2023-53	Formulation process of Decree No. 9,203, of November 22, 2017.	https://buscalai.cgu.gov.br/PedidosLai/DetailePedido?id=6110532
11/23/2017	Brazilian norm	Decreto nº 9.203	Establishes the governance policy for the direct, autonomous, and foundational federal public administration, with emphasis on integrity, risk management, and internal control.	https://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/_ato2015-2018/2017/decreto/d9203.htm
2/15/2018	Information on formulation process	Process # 00106.018542-2023-55	Formulation process of CGU Ordinance No. 1,089, of April 25, 2018.	https://buscalai.cgu.gov.br/PedidosLai/DetailePedido?id=6110533
4/1/2018	CGU guidance	Guia Prático da Implementação de Programas de Integridade Pública	Provides step-by-step guidance for implementing public integrity programs within federal government agencies, aligned with Decree No. 9,203/2017. It focuses on diagnosis, planning, implementation, and monitoring.	https://www.gov.br/cgu/pt-br/centrais-de-conteudo/publicacoes/integridade/arquivos/integridade-2018.pdf

4/13/2018	Publication on free press or government websites	CGU discute implantação dos programas de integridade nos órgãos e entidades federais	The CGU hosted an event to launch regulatory guidelines for implementing integrity programs, including panels, training sessions, and the presentation of best practices.	https://www.gov.br/cgu/pt-br/assuntos/noticias/2018/04/cgu-discute-implantacao-dos-programas-de-integridade-nos-orgaos-federais
4/26/2018	Brazilian norm	Portaria CGU nº 1.089	Provides guidance for agencies and entities to implement integrity measures and structure integrity plans within the direct federal public administration. Partially revoked by Ordinance No. 57/2019.	https://repositorio.cgu.gov.br/bitstream/1/45187/3/Portaria_1089_2018_CGU.pdf
10/1/2018	CGU guidance	Guia Prático de Gestão de Riscos para a Integridade	Presents a simplified approach to risk management applied to integrity policies, supporting public agencies in identifying, analyzing, and mitigating integrity-related risks.	https://www.gov.br/cgu/pt-br/centrais-de-conteudo/publicacoes/integridade/arquivos/manual-gestao-de-riscos.pdf
1/4/2019	Information on formulation process	Process # 00106.018543-2023-08	Formulation process of CGU Ordinance No. 57, of January 4, 2019.	https://buscalai.cgu.gov.br/PedidosLai/DetailPedido?id=6110537
1/7/2019	Brazilian norm	Portaria CGU nº 57	Amends Ordinance No. 1,089/2018 to further detail the implementation and monitoring of integrity plans in federal executive agencies and entities.	https://repositorio.cgu.gov.br/bitstream/1/45186/3/Portaria_CGU_57_2019.pdf
4/1/2019	Publication on free press or government websites	CGU participa do Fórum Global de Integridade e Anticorrupção da OCDE	CGU representatives attended the OECD Global Integrity Forum in Paris, showcasing Brazil's anti-corruption initiatives, including leniency agreements and the use of technology.	https://www.gov.br/cgu/pt-br/assuntos/noticias/2019/04/cgu-participa-do-forum-global-de-integridade-e-anticorrupcao-da-ocde
6/1/2019	CGU guidance	Guia Prático das Unidades de Gestão da Integridade	Offers practical guidance for structuring Integrity Management Units (USIs), including their roles, responsibilities, and coordination with other internal control and integrity functions.	https://www.gov.br/cgu/pt-br/centrais-de-conteudo/publicacoes/integridade/arquivos/unidades-de-gestao.pdf
9/19/2019	Information on formulation process	Process # 00106.003623/2024-31	Information about the CGU-OECD project on federal public service values.	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19582555
9/29/2019	Information on formulation process	Process # 00106.003530-2024-15	CGU processes and documents that led to the OECD report <i>Strengthening Public Integrity in Brazil: Mainstreaming Integrity Policies in the Federal Executive Branch</i> .	https://buscalai.cgu.gov.br/PedidosLai/DetailPedido?id=7011905
10/1/2019	CGU guidance	Como Implementar uma Corregedoria em Municípios – Versão Completa	Provides guidance to municipalities, especially larger ones, on how to create and structure internal affairs units (<i>corregedorias</i>), focusing on disciplinary and punitive measures against misconduct by public officials and legal entities.	https://repositorio.cgu.gov.br/bitstream/1/44489/7/1_Manual_Como_implementar_uma_corregedoria_em_munic%C3%ADpios_vers%C3%A3o_completa.pdf
3/12/2020	International standards / assessments	The OECD Public Integrity Handbook	The handbook offers practical guidance to help governments implement the 2017 OECD Recommendation on Public Integrity. It elaborates on concepts, tools, and institutional arrangements for building coherent and effective integrity systems.	https://www.oecd.org/content/dam/oecd/en/publications/reports/2020/05/oecd-public-integrity-handbook_598692a5/ac8ed8e8-en.pdf
8/27/2020	Information on formulation process	Process # 00106.018544-2023-44	Formulation process of Decree No. 10,756, of July 27, 2021.	https://buscalai.cgu.gov.br/PedidosLai/DetailPedido?id=6110538
10/28/2020	Information on formulation process	Process # 00106.002583/2024-19	Copy of the case file in which “DTC Order 1693116” is included.	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19582555
11/17/2020	Information on formulation process	Process # 00137.014195-2023-24	Formulation process of Decree No. 10,756, of July 27, 2021.	https://buscalai.cgu.gov.br/PedidosLai/DetailPedido?id=6110541

12/1/2020	CGU guidance	Sete Passos para Criar uma Ouvidoria no Meu Município	A step-by-step manual for municipal governments to establish ombudsman offices, aimed at improving citizen engagement, social oversight, and transparency mechanisms.	https://www.gov.br/ouvidorias/pt-br/central-de-conteudos/biblioteca/arquivos/ouvidoria-no-meu-municipio-completo-2020.pdf
4/1/2021	Brazilian norm	Lei nº 14.133	New Public Procurement and Administrative Contracts Law, replacing Law No. 8,666/1993, with provisions related to integrity, governance, and risk management.	https://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/ato2019-2022/2021/lei/l14133.htm
5/28/2021	Information on formulation process	Process # 18002.002665-2023-06	Formulation process of Decree No. 10,756, of July 27, 2021.	https://buscalai.cgu.gov.br/PedidosLai/DetailePedido?id=6110540
7/27/2021	Brazilian norm	Decreto nº 10.756	Establishes the Public Integrity System of the Federal Executive Branch (SIPEF), defining objectives, structures, and responsibilities for coordinating integrity actions.	http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/ato2019-2022/2021/decreto/d10756.htm
7/27/2021	Publication on free press or government websites	Governo Federal lança Sistema de Integridade Pública do Poder Executivo Federal (Sipef)	The federal government launched the Public Integrity System (SIPEF) to standardize and strengthen integrity programs in federal agencies, with a focus on governance, risk management, and corruption prevention.	https://www.gov.br/cgu/pt-br/assuntos/noticias/2021/07/governo-federal-lanca-sistema-de-integridade-publica-do-poder-executivo-federal-sipef
7/28/2021	Publication on free press or government websites	Sistema de Integridade Pública do Executivo Federal ampliará prevenção da corrupção no Brasil	The SIPEF system is expected to strengthen corruption prevention by providing guidelines and monitoring the implementation of integrity programs across federal institutions.	https://www.gov.br/cgu/pt-br/assuntos/noticias/2021/07/sistema-de-integridade-publica-do-executivo-federal-ampliara-prevencao-da-corrupcao-no-brasil
8/4/2021	Publication on free press or government websites	Judiciário passa a contar com Sistema de Integridade para o combate à corrupção	The National Council of Justice (CNJ) implemented a Judicial Integrity System to promote ethics, transparency, and corruption prevention in Brazil's judiciary.	https://www.conjur.com.br/2021-ago-04/judiciario-passa-contar-sistema-integridade-corrupcao/
8/16/2021	Information on formulation process	Process # 00106.003534/2024-95	Information on the CGU's work related to the OECD Public Integrity Panel.	https://buscalai.cgu.gov.br/PedidosLai/DetailePedido?id=7012347
8/21/2021	Brazilian norm	Resolução CNJ nº 410	Provides general rules for the Integrity System of the Judiciary, with guidelines for corruption prevention, the promotion of ethics, and internal control mechanisms.	https://atos.cnj.jus.br/atos/detalhar/4073
12/8/2021	International standards / assessments	Strengthening Public Integrity in Brazil: Mainstreaming Integrity Policies in the Federal Executive Branch	This report evaluates the implementation of Brazil's integrity strategy in the federal executive branch and recommends ways to improve coordination, monitoring, and engagement, particularly under the SIPEF framework.	https://www.oecd.org/content/dam/oecd/en/publications/reports/2021/12/strengthening-public-integrity-in-brazil_e7d2d27b/a8cbb8fa-en.pdf
12/9/2021	Brazilian norm	Decreto nº 10.889	Regulates provisions of Law No. 12,813/2013 regarding conflicts of interest, public engagement schedules, and hospitality offered by private entities. It also establishes the Electronic Scheduling System (e-Agendas) in the Federal Executive Branch.	https://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/ato2019-2022/2021/decreto/d10889.htm
12/14/2021	Publication on free press or government websites	CGU participa do lançamento do Portal de Indicadores de Integridade da OCDE	The CGU took part in the launch of the OECD Public Integrity Indicators Portal, which assesses anti-corruption maturity and audit efficiency. The indicators are intended to guide improvements in Brazil's public policies.	https://www.gov.br/cgu/pt-br/assuntos/noticias/2021/12/cgu-participa-do-lancamento-do-portal-de-indicadores-de-integridade-da-ocde

1/17/2022	Brazilian norm	Portaria CNJ nº 9 de 2022	Designates the Judiciary's Integrity Commission, responsible for implementing and monitoring actions related to integrity, ethics, and transparency within the National Council of Justice (CNJ).	https://atos.cnj.jus.br/atos/detalhar/4315
1/27/2022	Publication on free press or government websites	CNJ define composição do Comitê de Integridade do Judiciário	The CNJ appointed members of the Judiciary's Integrity Committee to oversee ethical and integrity initiatives within the judicial system.	https://www.conjur.com.br/2022-jan-28/cnj-define-composicao-comite-integridade-poder-judiciario/
3/24/2022	Brazilian norm	Portaria Normativa CGU nº 6	Establishes the Time Brasil Program, which enables the CGU to foster, support, and guide subnational governments in promoting transparency, integrity, and social participation as pillars of the Open Government Partnership.	https://repositorio.cgu.gov.br/xmlui/bitstream/handle/1/67770/Portaria_normativa_6_2022.pdf?sequence=3&isAllowed=y
7/29/2022	International standards / assessments	The OECD Economics Working Paper No. 1725: Anti-Corruption and Public Integrity Strategies – Insights from New OECD Indicators	This working paper presents findings from the OECD Public Integrity Indicators project. It emphasizes weaknesses in national strategic frameworks, noting that although many countries adopt anti-corruption strategies, their implementation and integration into broader public governance remain weak.	https://www.oecd.org/content/dam/oecd/en/publications/reports/2022/08/anti-corruption-and-public-integrity-strategies-insights-from-new-oecd-indicators_874e08c1/a925c7fd-en.pdf
3/7/2023	Information on formulation process	Process # 00106.003622/2024-97	Case file mentioned in the DOCX files made available by the MGI in response to request for information No. 18002.002666/2023-42.	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19582555
3/24/2023	Information on formulation process	Process # 18002.002666-2023-42	Formulation process of Decree No. 11,529, of May 16, 2023.	https://buscalai.cgu.gov.br/PedidosLai/DetailPedido?id=6110543
5/15/2023	Information on formulation process	Process # 00106.018545-2023-99	Formulation process of Decree No. 11,529, of May 16, 2023.	https://buscalai.cgu.gov.br/PedidosLai/DetailPedido?id=6110542
5/16/2023	Publication on free press or government websites	Decreto institui novo Conselho de Transparência do Executivo Federal	A decree established the new Transparency, Integrity, and Anti-Corruption Council (CTICC), expanding civil society participation in CGU-related policy discussions.	https://www.gov.br/cgu/pt-br/assuntos/noticias/2023/05/decreto-institui-novo-conselho-de-transparencia-do-executivo-federal
5/16/2023	Brazilian norm	Decreto nº 11.529	Establishes the Public Integrity Program of the Federal Executive Branch, revokes Decree No. 10,756/2021 (SIPEF), and defines new guidelines to promote integrity, ethics, and good governance in public administration.	https://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/_ato2023-2026/2023/decreto/D11529.htm
5/26/2023	Publication on free press or government websites	CGU participa de evento da OCDE sobre integridade e combate à corrupção	The CGU attended the OECD Global Anti-Corruption and Integrity Forum to discuss international cooperation, climate crises, and best practices in auditing and compliance.	https://www.gov.br/cgu/pt-br/assuntos/noticias/2023/05/cgu-participa-de-evento-da-ocde-sobre-integridade-e-combate-a-corrupcao
6/19/2023	Brazilian norm	Lei nº 14.600	Establishes the basic organizational structure of the Presidency of the Republic and the Ministries, including amendments to and revocations of various laws; reorganizes institutional structures with implications for governance and integrity.	https://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/_ato2023-2026/2023/lei/L14600.htm
9/14/2023	Information on formulation process	Process # 00106.001413/2024-17	Documents on the formulation of the CTICC Work Plan 2024–2026.	https://buscalai.cgu.gov.br/PedidosLai/DetailPedido?id=6818818

9/22/2023	International standards / assessments	Description of the OECD Public Integrity Indicators Project	This technical overview describes the structure, scope, and methodological foundations of the OECD's Public Integrity Indicators, which are designed to measure both <i>de jure</i> and <i>de facto</i> elements of public integrity frameworks across countries.	https://oecd-public-integrity-indicators.org/indicators
9/22/2023	International standards / assessments	The OECD Public Integrity Indicators: Harnessing Data to Measure Corruption Risks and Public Integrity Safeguards	This presentation outlines a new generation of OECD indicators that measure corruption risks and integrity safeguards. It emphasizes a shift from perception-based advocacy to actionable, evidence-based policy tools.	https://www.unodc.org/documents/commissions/CCPCJ/CCPCJ_Sessions/CCPCJ_32/ISM_TD_Kyoto/Statements/11_Janos_FINAL_PII_-_Kyoto_presentation.pdf
12/8/2023	CGU guidance	Modelo de Maturidade em Integridade Pública (MMIP) – Referencial Técnico – Versão 1.0	Introduces a structured framework for evaluating and enhancing organizational maturity in public integrity. It defines key elements and maturity levels to support robust and effective integrity management aligned with SITA (Decree No. 11,529/2023).	https://repositorio.cgu.gov.br/xmlui/bitstream/handle/1/92957/MMIP_SIP_2024.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y